

Solar ephemeris for calculating the gravitational light deflexion

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Introduction

To calculate the relativistic light deflexion by the Sun it is necessary to know the satellitocentric coordinate of the Sun to a certain accuracy. As it turns out, it is not acceptable to equate the Sun's position with the Solar System Barycentre. Since the barycentre (rather than the Sun) is the origin of our reference frame, we need an algorithm for computing the barycentric position of the Sun, $b_S(T)$. The required accuracy is 100 Mm or better (corresponding to $< 10 \mu\text{s}$ error in the deflexion). This note derives the requirements for the calculation of b_S . A Fortran subroutine (SUN) has been constructed (Lindegren, 1984 June 15) which should give the barycentric position to better than 1 Mm.

Accuracy requirement

The gravitational deflexion by the Sun is approximately

$$D = (4.07 \text{ mas}) \cot^2(\frac{1}{2}\theta) \quad (1)$$

if θ is the satellitocentric angle between the Sun and the star. Since $\theta \geq \frac{1}{2}\pi - \xi = 47^\circ$, we have

$$\left| \frac{dD}{d\theta} \right| = (4.07 \text{ mas})(1 - \cos \theta)^{-1} < 12.8 \text{ mas rad}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, in order to get D to 0.01 mas (say), we need θ to $7.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ rad (worst case), corresponding to about 100 Mm at a distance of 1 au.

Calculation of b_S

Let m_i , h_i be the mass and heliocentric position of planet i , and m_S the mass of the Sun. The barycentric position of the Sun is then

$$b_S = - (m_S + \sum_{i>0} m_i)^{-1} \sum_{i>0} m_i h_i \quad (3)$$

The amplitude of the contribution from any given planet is approximately $(m_i/m_S)a_i$, with a_i the mean distance from the Sun. See Table 1.

TABLE 1. Contributions to $\underline{b}_S$ of the various planets

planet (i)	a_i [au]	m_S/m_i (IAU 1976) -	m_S/m_i (DE200) -	$(m_i/m_S)a_i$ [Mm]	Δ [Mm]
1 Mercury	0.39	6023600	6023600	0.01	0.00
2 Venus	0.72	408523.5	408523.5	0.27	0.00
3 Earth	1.00	328900.5	328900.55	0.46	-0.00
4 Mars	1.52	3098710	3098710	0.07	0.00
5 Jupiter	5.20	1047.355	1047.350	745	+0.04
6 Saturn	9.57	3498.5	3498.0	410	+0.06
7 Uranus	19.3	22869	22960	127	-0.51
8 Neptune	30.3	19314	19314	235	0.00
9 Pluto	40	3000000	13000000	2.0	-1.95

The last column gives the difference in $(m_i/m_S)a_i$ when the DE200 mass is used instead of the IAU mass. Concerning the mass of Pluto it should be noted that the IAU value was adopted before the discovery of the satellite Charon, and that the DE200 value (from the motion of the satellite) must be considered more definitive.

It is evident from the table that the four giant planets ($i = 5$ to 8) at least must be included in the calculation of $\underline{b}_S$ in order to satisfy the primary requirement (max error < 100 Mm). If the mass of Pluto is taken to be negligible, this automatically gives a maximum error of the order of 1 Mm. The major errors or uncertainties are then the mass of Uranus and the contribution from the Earth (including the Moon).

Concerning Uranus, it is appropriate to calculate $\underline{b}_S$ with the same mass as is used for the barycentric Earth ephemeris; in this way, there is no direct bias in the geocentric position of the Sun resulting from using different mass values. (The same argument applies to Jupiter and Saturn, although the effects are smaller here.) If the Earth ephemeris by Chapront et al. (1984) is adopted (rather than DE200), then the IAU masses should be used for the giant planets.

The contribution by the Earth+Moon has an amplitude corresponding to a maximum error in the deflexion of 0.05 μ s. Still, it could be included quite easily by calculating the satellitocentric coordinate of the Sun as

$$\underline{s}_S = \underline{b}_S - 1.00000304 \underline{b}_O \quad (4)$$